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TABLE OF CONTENTS

<i>Maksymilian Górski</i> , BLIND SIGNATURES FOR PRIVACY-PRESERVING E- PRESCRIPTIONS	4
<i>Ofunneka Jennifer Okonkwoabutu</i> , A STUDY OF POST-HOC EXPLAINABLE AI METHODS FOR AN AUDIO DEEPFAKE DETECTION FRAMEWORK	8
<i>Marta Narigina, Heinrihs Kristians Skrodelis</i> , SECURING PATIENT DIGITAL TWINS THROUGH IOT: CYBERSECURITY APPROACHES FOR REMOTE HEALTH MONITORING	12
<i>Maciej Kisielewicz</i> , SECURITY RISKS IN MEDICAL IOT DEVICES	21
<i>Malwina Ewa Kołodziejczak</i> , CYBER WARFARE IN THE REPUBLIC OF POLAND: ACTIONS IN CYBERSPACE THAT COULD LEAD TO THE MARTIAL LAW	26
<i>Zbyněk Lička, Kamil Malinka, Anton Firc</i> , ZERO-SHOT SOURCE SPEECH RECONSTRUCTION: A WORK-IN-PROGRESS LOOK	30

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EUDI Wallet, Privacy Preservation,
Cryptography, e-Prescription,
Blind Signatures, eIDAS-2

Maksymilian GORSKI

BLIND SIGNATURES FOR PRIVACY-PRESERVING E-PRESCRIPTIONS

ABSTRACT:

Under the European Parliament's eIDAS-2 regulation [1], European Digital Identity Wallets will be introduced across European Union member states. Their purpose is to enable citizens to maintain complete control over their digital identity. The requirements presented in [1] also introduce the requirement for modifications to currently utilized electronic services to ensure user privacy. This manuscript undertakes the challenge of designing a service for issuing and filling e-Prescriptions based on cryptographic privacy-preserving mechanisms such as Blind Signatures. As part of this work, an e-Prescription service scheme was developed in the form of Qualified Electronic Attestation of Attributes, ensuring privacy of user data during the receiving, storing, and filling of the e-Prescriptions.

1. PRIVACY-PRESERVING MECHANISMS FOR EUROPEAN DIGITAL IDENTITY WALLETS

1.1. LEGISLATIVE BACKGROUND

In 2024, the European Parliament enacted a regulation establishing the European Digital Identity Framework, referred to as eIDAS-2 [1]. It mandates the implementation of European Digital Identity Wallets across European Union member states, providing citizens with tools for managing identity attributes in accordance with the Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) paradigm. Both identity wallets and services operating within their ecosystem should support solutions, including cryptographic mechanisms, that ensure user privacy.

1.2. PRIVACY PRESERVATION ACCORDING TO EIDAS-2

According to the eIDAS-2 regulation [1], the architecture for obtaining, processing, and presenting identity attributes and credentials should include mechanisms preventing the tracking and correlation of transactions performed by users of the identity wallet. As part of the initiative to implement European Digital Identity Wallets in member states, The European Digital Identity Wallet Architecture and Reference Framework (ARF) [2] was established as a standard for creating identity wallet services. A group of cryptography experts indicated an insufficient level of privacy resulting from the default privacy mechanisms proposed in publication [3]. Several cryptographic mechanisms ensuring user privacy were highlighted for potential application, among which Blind Signatures were included.

2. PRIVACY-PRESERVING QEAA E-PRESCRIPTIONS USING BLIND SIGNATURES

2.1. BLIND SIGNATURES AS PRIVACY-PRESERVING MECHANISMS FOR E-PRESCRIPTIONS

The author's attention was focused on creating an e-Prescription service in the form of Qualified Electronic Attestation of Attributes as defined in [1] and [2]. The proposed scheme employs Schnorr Blind Signatures [4] as the underlying cryptographic mechanism. However, any Blind Signatures scheme meeting the requirements for unlinkability of e-Prescription issuance transactions could be utilized. This concept aligns with the "cryptographic agility" approach postulated in ARF [2] for the entire european digital identity wallet architecture.

2.2. PRIVACY-PRESERVING QUALIFIED ATTESTATION OF ATTRIBUTES FOR E-PRESCRIPTIONS

As part of the e-Prescription service design, the schemes in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 were proposed, corresponding to two phases of the e-Prescription lifecycle: issuance (Fig. 1) and filling (Fig. 2). The Blind Signature protocol is employed during the issuance phase. An entity authorized to issue prescriptions, such as a certified physician, using an authenticated terminal, requests the issuance of an e-Prescription using the Blind Signature protocol. This means that only the party sending the request (e.g., doctor) and the target identity wallet user (e.g., patient) possess knowledge about the e-Prescription content until the attribute is presented to the Relying Party (e.g., pharmacy).

Due to the specific nature of the e-Prescription use-case, an additional mechanism is required to verify whether a particular e-Prescription has not been revoked. This mechanism is necessary to mitigate the double-spending threat, as well as to enable the revocation of an e-Prescription by an authorized entity, for instance, in case of an error. Simultaneously, the mechanism responsible for e-Prescription revocation must not violate the privacy requirements and transaction unlinkability during their issuance.

Fig. 1. Privacy-Preserving e-Prescription issuance process.

Fig. 2. Privacy-Preserving e-Prescription filling process.

The revocation of e-Prescriptions in the proposed scheme presented in Fig. 2 is implemented through maintaining a central list of e-Prescription identifiers that have already been used. Each e-Prescription should possess a unique identifier provided by the central e-Prescription revocation system. Each identifier generated and delivered to an entity authorized to issue e-Prescriptions is unique and corresponds with a qualified electronic signature, preventing forgery and ensuring the authenticity of the generated identifier.

3. POTENTIAL THREATS AND FUTURE WORKS

The current proposal for a privacy-preserving e-Prescription scheme remains vulnerable to potential abuses related to insufficient preservation of user privacy. The current solution is based on a scenario where any party can act as a potential attacker; however, it does not collaborate with other parties to acquire additional information about transactions. As part of the project development, a thorough security analysis is required in scenarios where an attacker has access to information from more than one party in the scheme.

An additional significant aspect is the fact that the unlinkability of e-Prescription issuance transactions depends on the size of the anonymity set created by all e-Prescription issuance transactions. Assuming a scenario in which e-Prescriptions are issued for only one user within a given time interval, they could be correlated to establish that user's identity.

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Key words:
Audio Deepfake Detection
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A Study of Post-Hoc Explainable AI Methods for an Audio Deepfake Detection Framework

ABSTRACT:

The increasing realism of synthesized speech generated by deepfake technologies has escalated security risks, enabling more convincing attacks such as impersonation and identity fraud. Although deep learning models have achieved impressive performance in detecting deep-fakes, most operate as *black boxes* and lack mechanisms for explainability. This limitation hinders trust, auditability, and broader adoption in high-stakes scenarios. In this study, we propose the integration of post-hoc explainable AI techniques with a Wav2Vec2BERT-based detection framework. This approach seeks to clarify model decision-making without compromising accuracy, thereby fostering transparency, interpretability, and resilience in audio deepfake detection systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deepfake audio poses a growing threat, driven by advancements in generative technologies capable of producing highly realistic synthetic speech. This audio is increasingly used in voice phishing, impersonation, and the circumvention of voice-based authentication systems[1]. In response to these concerns, state-of-the-art audio deepfake detection methods have been developed and have demonstrated strong performance on benchmark datasets[2]. However, while many of these models generalize well across diverse datasets and synthesis techniques, their lack of transparency in decision-making limits their effectiveness in critical scenarios where explainability is as important as accuracy[2, 3].

Recent studies have shown that Wave2Vec2BERT framework[4] offers improved robustness to real-world audio corruptions and generalizes well on existing deepfake datasets[3]. However, its accuracy drops against advanced synthetic speech like Seed-TTS[5], and its black-box nature limits trust in sensitive applications[6].

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1.1. DEEPFAKE AUDIO DETECTION

Deepfake audio detection is an increasingly important task as synthetic speech becomes more convincing and widely used. Various approaches have been proposed for detecting synthetic audio. Some traditional deep learning methods specifically designed for deepfake audio detection often rely on engineered acoustic features e.g. Linear Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (LFCC)[7] or visual representations such as spectrograms, which are then classified using convolutional or recurrent neural networks[3]. Some other models such as RawNet2[8], RawGAT-ST[9], and AASIST[10] take raw waveforms and classify them using CNN, CNN with attention-based graph and self-attention mechanism respectively.

Some pre-trained models such as Wav2Vec2[11], Whisper[12], and Wav2Vec2BERT[4], for example, have been fine-tuned for deepfake detection tasks, showing significant performance[3] and these directly process raw waveforms and use transformer-based architectures. Although these models have achieved strong performance on specific datasets, they frequently suffer from poor generalization across different types of deepfakes and lack transparency in their decision-making[3]. Models that perform well on one synthesis method may fail on others and often struggle to maintain performance under real-world conditions such as noise, modifications, or compression, limiting their practical use. Wav2Vec2BERT was found to perform better in most conditions[3].

Beyond achieving high accuracy, a critical challenge in audio deepfake detection is ensuring model explainability. Deep learning models such as Wav2Vec2-BERT[4] are known for their strong representational power but often function as "black boxes," making their decisions difficult to interpret[13]. This lack of transparency is especially concerning in high-stakes applications like law enforcement, journalism, and content moderation, where understanding *why* a decision is made is as important as the decision itself[13]. In security-sensitive contexts such as forensic analysis or voice-based authentication, the opacity of these models can undermine user trust and hinder adoption. Therefore, integrating post hoc explainable AI (XAI) techniques is essential to provide interpretable explanations without altering the underlying model behavior.

2. Explainable AI (XAI)

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) aims to make machine learning models more transparent by revealing the reasoning behind their decisions. Various XAI methods have been developed to support different use cases, each employing distinct approaches to enhance model transparency. These methods are generally classified into two main categories: *ante hoc* methods, which are inherently interpretable by design, and *post hoc* methods, which generate explanations after the model has been trained[14]. Post hoc methods are particularly valuable for interpreting complex, black-box models, as they do not require access to the model internals or retraining. XAI methods are further categorized by scope (i.e. local, global, cohort) and approach (i.e. model-specific vs. model-agnostic)[14]. The scope refers to the level at which the explanation is provided. Local methods explain individual predictions. Global methods describe how the model behaves overall. Cohort-based methods focus on groups of similar instances. The approach indicates how the explanation is generated. Model-agnostic methods treat the model as a black box and use only its inputs

and outputs. Model-specific methods require access to internal components such as gradients, layers, or activations.

This study will investigate both model-specific and model-agnostic post hoc explainability techniques for interpreting predictions made by the Wave2Vec2-BERT model in audio deepfake detection. These methods are suitable when retraining the model is not feasible and transparency is needed after deployment. We will evaluate model-agnostic methods such as LIME[15], SHAP[16], Anchors[17], and decision tree surrogates[18]. These techniques rely only on the inputs and outputs of the model. We also explore model-specific approaches, including Class Activation Mapping (CAM)[19] and Grad-CAM[20]. These methods use internal gradients and activations to generate saliency maps, which are particularly useful when audio is represented as spectrograms. By comparing both categories, we aim to assess their strengths and limitations in enhancing interpretability. Our goal is to build a detection framework that is both accurate and explainable and address a key limitation in current deepfake detection systems.

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Key words:

Digital Twins, IoMT, Cybersecurity, Blockchain, Healthcare Monitoring, Post-Quantum Cryptography, AI, Privacy, HIPAA, GDPR

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SECURING PATIENT DIGITAL TWINS THROUGH IOT: CYBERSECURITY APPROACHES FOR REMOTE HEALTH MONITORING

ABSTRACT:

A game-changing tool for IoT-enabled remote health monitoring are digital twins (DTs), which are dynamic virtual representations of actual patients or medical equipment. Patient DTs enable predictive analytics and personalized care by combining continuous IoT sensor data (from wearables and implants, for example) with electronic health records. But there are also significant cybersecurity issues brought about by this integration of private health data. In order to preserve patient privacy in accordance with laws like HIPAA, GDPR, and FDA guidelines, as well as to ensure resilience to attacks, we examine the state of the art in securing patient DTs and IoMT systems. We use recent case studies (such as blockchain-based DTs, AI-powered DT frameworks, and IoMT system fault analyses) to demonstrate these problems. Lastly, we suggest a multifaceted approach to security. This covers blockchain for audit and trust, AI/ML anomaly detection, encryption and robust authentication, and the switch to quantum-safe cryptography. According to the paper, post-quantum algorithms, blockchain-enabled access control, and AI-driven monitoring, when combined with adherence to data-protection standards, can help reduce the ever-evolving cybersecurity threats in healthcare digital twins.

1.INTRODUCTION

Originally employed in industry and aerospace, digital twin (DT) technology has recently drawn interest in the healthcare sector as a means of simulating and replicating patient physiology for improved monitoring and care [1]. In order to provide re-

mote monitoring and individualized insights, a patient DT continuously consumes clinical records and IoT/IoMT data (wearables, biosensors) [2]. For instance, a patient's DT can be fed data from smart-home and hospital sensors to track vital signs or glucose levels in real time [3]. New telemedicine and preventive-care applications are supported by the convergence of IoT, AI, and DTs. Despite its potential, there are significant security and privacy risks associated with DT integration in the healthcare industry. Because patient data is so sensitive, cyberattacks could compromise confidentiality or interfere with vital systems. The attack surface is increased by the DT concept's reliance on cloud analytics and connected devices. Furthermore, stringent controls are enforced by health regulations: frameworks must adhere to FDA, GDPR, HIPAA, and other data protection standards [4]. According to earlier research, early healthcare DT pilots need to address issues with access control, secure data integration, and regulatory compliance.

This paper examines current cybersecurity threats and solutions for IoT-enabled patient DTs in this context. We describe the main problems (Section 3), provide examples of them using recent case studies (Section 4), and make suggestions (Section 5) that center on innovative solutions such as post-quantum cryptography, blockchain trust, and AI-driven detection.

2.BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

IoT and IoMT in healthcare: By combining wearable and implantable medical devices, the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) expands on the original Internet of Things. Continuous vital-sign data is collected by IoMT devices (smartwatches, insulin pumps, remote monitors, etc.) and sent to clinicians [5]. These systems allow for round-the-clock patient monitoring outside of clinical settings by obfuscating the distinction between homes and hospitals. A network/gateway layer, cloud servers, and a "thing layer" of body sensors make up the typical IoMT infrastructure [6]. More timely care is provided by the resulting data-rich environment, but each layer is susceptible to errors and attacks (e.g. sensor failure, router outages, ISP issues).

Digital twins of patients: In the medical field, a DT can be thought of as a virtual patient model that replicates the physiology and behaviors of an actual patient. Lab results, imaging, streaming sensor data, and electronic health records are examples of heterogeneous data that DTs integrate. They facilitate sophisticated analytics: The DT's AI and machine learning algorithms can simulate the effects of treatment or forecast how a disease will progress. Use cases for DT in practice include emergency response, surgical planning, and the management of chronic diseases (such as diabetes monitoring). To accomplish real-time monitoring, recent frameworks integrate cloud

computing, IoT, and DTs. For instance, one system continuously recorded temperature, SpO₂, and HR data from 20 people, adding it to historical EHR data.

Technologies that enable: Key enablers for DTs include edge/cloud computing, 5G/6G connectivity, IoT sensor networks, and artificial intelligence. Because AI/ML can analyze incoming data and identify health abnormalities or cyberthreats, it is particularly important [7].

Proposals for blockchain-secured patient DTs demonstrate how blockchain is becoming a tool for data integrity and decentralized access control [8]. New security requirements are brought about by these technologies, though (e.g. key management for encryption, trust in federated AI models). The importance of cybersecurity in digital health is already being emphasized by governments and regulators; for instance, FDA guidance now mandates that cybersecurity risk analyses be included in device submissions. All things considered, the healthcare DT landscape is still developing, and its security frameworks need to change quickly to stay up with emerging technologies [9].

3.CORE CYBERSECURITY CHALLENGES

In order to secure IoT-enabled patient DTs, several interconnected issues must be resolved:

Data integrity and confidentiality: Patient DTs deal with extremely private information; breaches may expose private medical records. Attackers might compromise gateways or listen in on sensor networks. By employing robust key-management and encrypting data both in transit and at rest, digital twins can reduce. But because they frequently lack hardware security, legacy IoMT devices are susceptible to tampering and interception. Maintaining data integrity is also essential because maliciously altered DT data may result in incorrect diagnoses. Digital signatures and cryptographic hashing along the data pipeline are examples of solutions, as are ongoing integrity checks in the DT simulation environment.

Resilience and availability: Medical monitoring needs to be very trustworthy. Patient care may be jeopardized if the DT's data feeds are interrupted by Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks or device malfunctions. Numerous single points of failure have been identified in studies of remote patient monitoring systems (home router outage, ISP disruption, cloud server downtime).

Redundancy and failover techniques are necessary to maintain availability. For instance, edge computing can locally buffer data during network outages, and DT frameworks can model the worst-case scenarios to pinpoint crucial failure modes.

Access control and authentication: Only authorized parties should have access to patient DT data. It is difficult to manage identities among automated agents, physi-

cians, and caregivers. Standard procedures include multi-factor authentication and role-based access control (RBAC). One recent DT system implemented stringent RBAC to guarantee that only authorized personnel could access a patient model. Unauthorized data queries or impersonation attacks may result from inadequate authentication.

Vulnerabilities in software and devices: Due to their limited resources and outdated firmware, many IoT devices are vulnerable to malicious updates and code injection. Networks of medical devices could be used by malware to spread. By testing device configurations and security patches in a virtual model prior to deployment, DT-based simulation could be beneficial.

However, patch management and standardization are made more difficult by the diversity of medical devices.

Privacy and adherence to the law: DT systems must respect patient privacy rights in addition to security. Data minimization and the use of privacy-enhancing technologies are required by modern regulations (HIPAA in the US and GDPR in the EU). This covers consent-driven data sharing guidelines and the pseudonymization or anonymization of health data when creating DTs.

One constant governance challenge is making sure DT data pipelines adhere to changing standards.

Interoperability and standardization: Integrating various devices and data sources can result in security flaws if common frameworks aren't used. Holistic security monitoring is hampered by closed or proprietary protocols. Smart health environments still frequently lack established security standards, despite industry efforts to address this (such as HL7 FHIR for healthcare data).

Threats from adversarial AI: AI models themselves turn into attack vectors as they become more and more integrated into DTs (e.g. poisoning of training data, model evasion). Strong machine learning techniques and ongoing model retraining are necessary for identifying unusual or malevolent data patterns. But depending too much on AI also brings up issues with bias and interpretability.

In conclusion, technical weaknesses (network attacks, device hijacking) and organizational problems (policy, compliance) comprise the main cybersecurity risks to IoT-enabled patient DTs. End-to-end security thinking, from sensors to the cloud, is necessary to address these.

4.CASE STUDIES

Blockchain-secured Patient Twin: According to Amofa et al. (2024), a patient DT architecture protected by smart contracts and blockchain is proposed. On-chain policies are designed to control changes to a patient's digital model, which combines

EHR and IoMT data. Smart contracts control the DT's query response and who can add data to it. This method offers decentralized access control and tamper-evident logging. The authors show how automating consent and audit procedures with a blockchain layer can enhance provenance and privacy. They assess storage overhead and latency, taking into account trade-offs while confirming viability. Without the need for a single reliable middleman, this example shows how decentralized ledgers can uphold policies and safeguard DT integrity.

IoMT Digital Twin Reference Architecture: For secure healthcare twins, Kabir and Ray (2024) offer a reference model named DT-IoMT. Their design combines a "secondary" digital twin that simulates hospital equipment and operations with a "primary" digital twin that simulates patient biosignals. The use of the DT environment to model cyberattacks and test safety mitigation techniques is a crucial component. For instance, they demonstrate how the DT can simulate various encryption techniques or denial-of-service attacks to assess the resilience of the system. The authors specifically link the DT's operations to the CIA triad: availability is guaranteed by redundant simulation of system failures, integrity is guaranteed by change-detection algorithms, and confidentiality is guaranteed by encryption and RBAC.

In medical IoT contexts, this case demonstrates how DTs themselves can be used as a sandbox for security testing.

IoMT Case of Resilient Heart Monitoring: To find failures, a recent IoMT study by Tomer et al. (2024) examines a real-world remote heart-monitoring scenario. In this instance, the clinic receives ECG data from a patient's wearable sensors via cloud servers, ISP networks, and home routers. The authors map necessary resilience strategies (e.g., access control at device/gateway, route optimization at network) and catalog failures at every layer, from device battery drain to cloud denial-of-service.

To dynamically reroute data and identify anomalies, they suggest combining AI, microservice architectures, and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) at edge nodes. This case illustrates the same multi-layered difficulties a patient DT must deal with, even though it is not a digital twin in the traditional sense. It emphasizes the significance of end-to-end design: to maintain the virtual patient's life and accuracy, secure IoMT links, ongoing monitoring, and automated recovery mechanisms are required.

AI-Powered DT Surveillance: A DT-based system continuously tracked the vital signs (heart rate, SpO₂, and temperature) and historical records of twenty participants in a pilot study conducted by Jameil and Al-Raweshidy (2025). By combining an MLP and XGBoost model, they were able to detect health anomalies with 98.9% accuracy. Importantly, they included encryption and regulatory protections in their design: the system was constructed in accordance with HIPAA/GDPR regulations, and data was encrypted and signed both in transit and at rest. Clinicians received anomaly alerts from the DT through a secure dashboard. This example illustrates a thorough DT implementation in which layered encryption protects confidentiality while machine

learning supports implicit security (such as anomaly detection in data streams) and health prediction.

5.RECOMMENDATIONS & IMPLEMENTATION BEST PRACTICES

Effective cybersecurity for healthcare IoT requires a layered pathway that begins with strong network boundaries, continues with continuous situational awareness, and culminates in forward-looking controls that keep pace with emerging threats. This chapter therefore progresses in three logical steps. Sub-section 5.1 sets the technical foundation by isolating devices and enforcing granular access, thereby shrinking the immediate attack surface. Sub-section 5.2 adds operational vigilance through monitoring, alerting and rapid response so that any breach of those boundaries is detected and contained early. Finally, sub-section 5.3 shifts the lens to strategic adaptations—cryptography, digital-twin security and quantum-resistant methods—ensuring that today’s safeguards evolve into tomorrow’s resilience. Readers can follow the chapter sequentially to move from “what to deploy now” toward “how to stay protected next”.

5.1 NETWORK SEGMENTATION AND ACCESS CONTROL

Implement micro-segmentation to isolate critical healthcare IoT devices, significantly reducing lateral threat movement and minimizing the overall attack surface [10].

Adopt blockchain-based access control solutions to ensure data integrity, accountability, and robust verification processes.

Utilize the Zero Trust model, enforcing continuous verification and strict access controls to reduce vulnerabilities [11].

Integrate intelligent threat detection platforms leveraging machine learning for real-time anomaly detection and adaptive response [12].

5.2 MONITORING, ALERTING, AND INCIDENT RESPONSE

Deploy AI-driven anomaly detection frameworks, including Deep Neural Networks and federated learning, achieving high accuracy and low false positives [13].

Adopt edge-based solutions (e.g., PRISM) for real-time threat detection, considering the necessity of model generalization for effective anomaly identification [14].

Implement incremental anomaly detection systems (PAC-based) to dynamically adjust to evolving IoT data patterns and threats [15].

Figure 1 illustrates the end-to-end healthcare IoT incident-response workflow, mapping each alert from initial detection through containment, eradication, recovery and continuous improvement.

Figure 1. Healthcare IoT Incident Response Flowchart

5.3 FUTURE TRENDS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Advance security measures for patient digital twins using blockchain and smart contracts to encapsulate data and manage IoT device access securely [16].

Employ optimized cryptographic techniques (e.g., homomorphic encryption, DDTHA, blowfish encryption) for secure data transmission and storage.

Integrate lightweight secure key establishment protocols (PUFs) to enhance IoMT network security against impersonation and replay attacks.

Proactively adopt emerging security technologies such as quantum-resistant cryptography and AI-enhanced predictive analytics to stay ahead of evolving cybersecurity threats.

Regularly update strategic risk assessments and adopt frameworks like RAMA and GOLD to effectively manage risks within a rapidly evolving cyber-threat landscape.

5.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In summary, this study emphasizes that securing patient digital twins for IoT-based remote health monitoring requires a multi-layered cybersecurity strategy. The most

critical measures include robust authentication and fine-grained access control so that only authorized entities interact with the twin, upholding patient privacy. Equally essential is end-to-end data protection – strong encryption and integrity checks on sensor data and twin databases that align with the CIA triad. Implementing proven cryptographic schemes and rigorous provenance tracking can bolster trust in the twin’s data by guaranteeing its integrity and origin. Continuous anomaly monitoring leverages the twin’s real-time analytics to flag suspicious deviations and alert providers to breaches or device malfunctions. Collectively, these approaches form a holistic defense-in-depth blueprint. Integrating them into patient digital-twin development will help keep systems confidential, tamper-resistant, and resilient during remote monitoring. The results underscore that security-by-design is imperative; embedding strict access policies and cryptographic safeguards at every layer preserve data accuracy and protect patient welfare while smoothing compliance with emerging cybersecurity requirements. Looking ahead, key areas of IoT security for patient twins remain underexplored. A primary gap is the absence of standardized frameworks tailored to digital-twin environments. Future work should focus on unified architectures that secure diverse IoMT devices by default and provide fail-safe responses to cyber incidents across healthcare platforms. Ensuring scalability and resilience such as - defending networks of patient twins against coordinated attacks - also demands further study. Emerging technologies likewise merit exploration to enhance twin security. On the regulatory front, the rapidly evolving landscape of data-protection and medical-device laws will shape research priorities. By addressing these open challenges, future studies can advance the safety, trust, and efficacy of patient digital twins. Ultimately, these efforts will pave the way for remote health-monitoring systems that are intelligent, personalized, secure, and compliant by design.

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Key words:
Cybersecurity, IoMT, Offensive Security, Health, Case Study

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SECURITY RISKS IN MEDICAL IOT DEVICES

ABSTRACT:

The rapid growth of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in healthcare introduces significant cybersecurity challenges. This paper examines critical security vulnerabilities in medical IoT devices, with particular emphasis on implantable and wearable systems such as pacemakers and insulin pumps. Through analysis of documented case studies and security research findings, we identify common vulnerability patterns including weak authentication mechanisms, lack of encryption, and inadequate network security configurations. My research demonstrates how these weaknesses can be exploited through techniques such as replay attacks, unauthorized device access, and protocol manipulation. We conclude with recommendations for enhanced security measures across technical, policy, and collaborative domains to safeguard patient safety and privacy in the expanding IoT healthcare ecosystem.

1. INTRODUCTION

The healthcare IoT market is experiencing exponential growth, projected to increase from approximately \$45.97 billion in 2023 to \$464.45 billion by 2034 [1]. This rapid expansion introduces significant security challenges, as medical devices increasingly integrate wireless communication capabilities, remote monitoring functions, and network connectivity. The consequences of security breaches in medical IoT devices extend beyond data privacy concerns to potential life-threatening scenarios for patients [2].

This research examines critical security vulnerabilities in medical IoT devices, focusing on implantable and wearable systems that directly impact patient health. The objectives of this study are to: (1) identify common security vulnerabilities in medical IoT devices, (2) analyze documented exploitation techniques and their potential impact, (3) evaluate existing security measures, and (4) propose enhanced security frameworks to mitigate risks.

2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Medical IoT devices encompass a wide range of technologies, from patient-worn monitors to implantable devices with complex interconnected systems. These devices typically operate within ecosystems involving multiple stakeholders, including patients, healthcare providers, device programmers, and vendor servers [3]. The communication infrastructure often involves home monitoring units (HMUs), wireless protocols, and cloud-based data storage and management systems.

The regulatory framework for medical devices, primarily overseen by organizations such as the FDA in the United States, involves comprehensive review processes. However, cybersecurity considerations have historically been secondary to functional safety and efficacy concerns [4]. Recent regulatory updates have begun to address this gap, with increased focus on security throughout the device lifecycle.

Previous research has identified numerous vulnerabilities in medical devices, with the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) database documenting specific instances affecting various medical systems. Notable examples include CVE-2018-10634, CVE-2018-14781, and CVE-2018-8849, which expose critical weaknesses in medical device firmware and communication protocols [5].

3. COMMON VULNERABILITY PATTERNS

My analysis reveals several recurring vulnerability patterns across different medical IoT devices:

1. **Weak authentication mechanisms:** Many devices rely on default or easily guessable passwords, with insufficient credential management and verification processes [6].
2. **Outdated or unpatched software:** Medical devices often operate on legacy systems with irregular update schedules, leaving known vulnerabilities unaddressed for extended periods [7].
3. **Lack of encryption for data transmission:** Patient data and device commands are frequently transmitted unencrypted, allowing for interception and manipulation [8].
4. **Hard-coded credentials:** Embedded authentication keys and passwords within device firmware prevent dynamic security updates and create systemic vulnerabilities [9].
5. **Poor network security configurations:** Inadequate network segmentation and access controls increase exposure to lateral movement attacks within healthcare infrastructure [10].

These vulnerabilities are particularly concerning in life-supporting or life-sustaining devices, where exploitation could directly impact patient safety.

4. CASE STUDIES AND VULNERABILITY ANALYSIS

4.1. INSULIN PUMP

In a landmark demonstration, security researcher Barnaby Jack highlighted critical vulnerabilities in wireless insulin pumps. Using custom antennas, he demonstrated the ability to compromise these devices from up to 300 feet away, bypassing security credentials and manipulating insulin delivery parameters [11]. The attack exploited unencrypted wireless communications and weak protocol implementations, allowing an attacker to potentially deliver fatal insulin doses to patients.

A more recent example involves the Insulet OmniPod insulin management system, where researchers identified vulnerabilities that allowed nearby attackers to schedule or immediately inject insulin without user authorization [12]. This replay attack exploited weak cryptographic protocols, permitting previously valid commands to be reused maliciously. Despite notification attempts beginning in November 2020, the vendor's delayed response highlighted challenges in vulnerability disclosure and remediation processes for medical devices.

4.2. PACEMAKER

Research on Medtronic pacemakers revealed vulnerabilities that could allow remote attackers to reprogram heart rhythms, potentially causing fatal disruptions [13]. Technical analysis identified unencrypted communications and lack of authentication for device commands as primary security weaknesses. While the FDA issued warnings and Medtronic subsequently released software updates, the case illustrated the persistent gap between identifying vulnerabilities and implementing effective remediations.

4.3. IMPLANTABLE MEDICAL DEVICE

Researchers from KU Leuven conducted comprehensive security analysis of proprietary protocols in implantable medical devices (IMDs), including pacemakers and neurostimulators [14]. By reverse-engineering communication protocols, they demonstrated how attackers could eavesdrop on communications, drain battery life, or disa-

ble therapies without requiring physical access to the devices. This case study emphasized that "security by obscurity" provides insufficient protection and highlighted the need for robust cryptographic protections in future device designs.

5. CONCLUSION

My research demonstrates that IoT medical devices remain vulnerable to various cybersecurity threats, with potentially severe consequences for patient safety. The case studies examined highlight recurring security challenges and the complexity of addressing them in the highly regulated and safety-critical healthcare environment.

The vulnerabilities identified pose significant implications for multiple stakeholders in the healthcare ecosystem. For patients, these security weaknesses create potential health risks and privacy concerns. For healthcare providers and institutions, they introduce liability issues and operational challenges. For manufacturers, they necessitate fundamental changes to design and development processes.

The evolving landscape of medical IoT security necessitates ongoing adaptation of in-depth security approaches as well as continuous research effort.

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Key words:
cyberwar, martial law, actions in cyberspace, legal basis

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CYBER WARFARE IN THE REPUBLIC OF POLAND: ACTIONS IN CYBERSPACE THAT COULD LEAD TO THE MARTIAL LAW

ABSTRACT:

This paper examines the legal and practical implications of cyber operations as potential triggers for the declaration of martial law in the Republic of Poland. Although current law allows for such a response in the case of external threats, including actions in cyberspace, it lacks a clear definition of what those actions entail. The absence of legal thresholds for the scale or impact of cyberattacks creates uncertainty. Drawing on EU regulations and cybersecurity frameworks, the paper highlights the need for more precise legal criteria to address modern hybrid threats.

1. LEGAL BASIS OF ACTIONS IN CYBERSPACE

The current statutory definition of martial law in Poland stipulates that the President of the Republic may, upon the request of the Council of Ministers, declare martial law in the event of an external threat to the state. This includes threats arising from terrorist activities or actions in cyberspace, armed aggression against the territory of the Republic of Poland, or obligations stemming from international agreements to participate in collective defense against aggression.

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According to Article 2(1a) of the relevant legislation, an external threat encompasses deliberate actions aimed at compromising the independence, territorial integrity, or significant economic interests of Poland, or actions intended to prevent or severely disrupt the normal functioning of the state, undertaken by entities external to Poland.

While the law provides a definition of cyberspace, it lacks a clear delineation of what constitutes "actions in cyberspace."

Firstly, the legislation offers a definitional explanation of cyberspace. Pursuant to Article 2(1b) of the aforementioned act, cyberspace is defined as the realm of information processing and exchange created by information and communication systems specified in Article 3(3) of the Act of February 17, 2005, on the computerization of activities of entities performing public tasks, along with the interconnections between them and their relationships with users. An information and communication system is described as a set of cooperating IT devices and software that ensures the processing, storage, as well as sending and receiving of data through telecommunications networks using appropriate terminal equipment for the given type of telecommunications network.

Secondly, it is noteworthy that only cyberspace is explicitly distinguished in the legislation, while other domains, such as outer space—already recognized in NATO doctrine—are omitted. Therefore, it would be consistent either to enumerate all relevant domains or to refrain from specifying any.

The realm of cyberspace constitutes a critical area of security and defense. The European Union's 2013 Cybersecurity Strategy emphasized the necessity of regulating principles concerning broadly understood cybersecurity. It highlighted that internet-based threats can have diverse origins and may cause disruptions not only in cyberspace but also in the physical world. These issues were addressed in the NIS Directive. Subsequently, the European Commission issued an implementing regulation outlining parameters to assess whether an incident is significant. When determining the significance of an incident, factors considered include the number of users affected, the duration of the incident, its geographical scope, and the extent of service disruption.

In response to these EU legislative initiatives, Poland was obliged to align its national legislation, which was accomplished through the Act of July 5, 2018, on the national cybersecurity system. This act introduced key definitions, such

as "critical incident" and "serious incident." However, the legislation does not establish a connection between specific types of incidents and the declaration of states of emergency. A significant issue is the absence of criteria defining the scale, consequences, or extent of damage caused by actions in cyberspace that would justify the declaration of martial law.

The Act of July 5, 2018, on the national cybersecurity system also organized the responsibilities of certain authorities in this domain.

The main research question concerns which activities in cyberspace could constitute grounds for the declaration of martial law—specifically, what scale, consequences, and objectives such activities would need to involve. The aim of the study is to identify the legal basis for actions undertaken in cyberspace and to attempt to define the scope, effects, and intentions that such actions should exhibit in order to be recognized as sufficient grounds for declaring martial law. The hypothesis assumes that activities in cyberspace are particularly difficult to assess in terms of whether they justify the introduction of martial law. It is highly probable that activities such as cybercrime, cyberterrorism, cyberespionage, disinformation, as well as cyberconflict or cyberwarfare—regardless of whether conducted by state-affiliated groups or non-state actors—would not meet the criteria for armed aggression or necessitate defense measures. Consequently, the declaration of a state of war or wartime conditions would not be warranted. The likelihood of declaring martial law is minimal, partly due to the challenges in identifying perpetrators. However, the situation would change if any activity in cyberspace were assessed as pre-war actions.

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Key words:
voice deepfakes, source speaker identification,
de-anonymization, forensics, source speaker tracing

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ZERO-SHOT SOURCE SPEECH RECONSTRUCTION: A WORK-IN-PROGRESS LOOK

ABSTRACT:

Developments in speech synthesis allow the creation of synthesized speech which is indistinguishable from real speech to a human listener. Unfortunately, such speech may be misused to manipulate or gain access past biometric systems. Extensive research has been done to create detection models with high accuracies which identify the presence of synthesized speech. The next step in this area of research is to not only detect the presence of synthesized utterances but also identify the adversary who produced them. This has been shown to be feasible for voice conversion methods. This work explores various existing approaches to linking attackers (source speakers) to voice-converted speech and proposes a general model-agnostic approach to reconstructing the source speech used to create malicious speech, which is currently under development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deepfakes are a category of synthetic content which is created using artificial intelligence in order to spoof or entertain a target listener. In this work, we mainly focus on a subcategory of deepfakes called spoofed (synthesized) speech. The quality of synthesized speech has reached a point where it cannot be distinguished by human listeners. Thus, voice deepfakes have become a significant security threat. There are several cases where attackers have used synthesized speech to scam their victims [1].

To combat this threat, methods for detecting synthesized speech have been explored by the community. However, detecting deepfakes can at best prevent a scam from happening. It would be beneficial if it were possible to link the perpetrators to malicious synthesized utterances in order to prosecute them for their malicious activ-

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ity. Luckily, it has been shown to be possible to some extent [2-4] for certain categories of speech synthesis methods – voice conversion.

Law enforcement could use methods for extracting source speaker identities from voice-converted speech to help their investigations. An example where such approaches are applicable is against vishing (voice phishing) attacks. The attackers must speak into a voice conversion system to communicate with their victims. By doing so, the attackers introduce their information into the converted speech and thus, their identity becomes extractable.

This work contains an overview of current approaches to identifying the original speaker in voice-converted speech. In addition, we propose a general approach to reconstructing the original speech used in the voice conversion process using a reversed voice-conversion pipeline.

2. RELATED WORK

Voice conversion (VC) is a category of speech synthesis methods whose task is to spoof a listener – make them believe the speech came from a target speaker.

VC methods can be split into several categories based on the number of speakers they are capable of converting across. VC works by introducing the target speaker style into extracted content information from the source speech and then synthesizing the combined features back into a waveform.

The most studied category of VC is any-to-any/zero-shot (A2A) VC. These methods are capable of introducing target speaker style using only one reference and no training. FreeVC [5] is a good example of A2A VC. The method uses an encoder-decoder architecture with a normalizing flow. An example of a non-traditional VC method is kNN-VC [6], which utilizes the k nearest neighbours algorithm to find corresponding feature vectors from the target speaker reference database (bag-of-vectors).

The VC task is to spoof a listener – make them believe the speech came from a target speaker. To perform this task effectively, the content, emotions, stress, etc., of the source speech needs to remain the same. The preservation of these aspects of speech introduces source speaker information into the converted speech. This allows the development of source speaker identification methods.

The source speaker identification task generally [2-4] considers an attacker using an open-source VC model for creating malicious speech. It is presumed that it is known the converted sample is synthesized, the attacker is the source speaker, and the attacker uses a voice conversion method to synthesize speech.

Fig. 1: A general source speaker verification system. The source speaker voice signature (embedding) is extracted from the converted speech. A suspect voice signature is extracted using the same model. The signatures are compared using a distance metric, resulting in a similarity score. Note that the suspect voice signature can be extracted using a different system. In such a case, the voice signatures of the same speaker must be matched during training.

3. SOURCE SPEAKER TRACING (SST)

The forensic task of identifying the original speaker in synthesized speech is called *Source Speaker Tracing (SST)*. SST can be broadly split into two categories: *Source Speaker Verification (SSV)* and *Source Speech Reconstruction (SSR)*.

Source Speaker Verification. SSV [2-4] is based on speaker verification systems, where a voice signature (a large vector, i.e. 512 dimensions) is created by the system, which can be compared with other speaker signatures using a distance metric. The distance metric then tells us how similar the two signatures are. When signatures are very close to each other, it means the signatures likely belong to the same speaker. Hence, SSV is only useful when there is another speaker (suspect) whose voice signature can be compared to the one extracted from a malicious recording.

A general example of such systems is shown in Fig. 1. The target speaker speech can be introduced to help filter out the target speaker style from the converted speech. Nonetheless, target speaker reference is not crucial to the functionality of SSV.

Source Speech Reconstruction. SSR, on the other hand, is an underexplored sub-field of SST. The main idea is that reconstructed speech is more presentable compared

to a voice signature, which is essentially a feature vector. In addition, reconstructed speech can be useful regardless of whether the suspect is known or not; knowing what the suspect might sound like can be useful by itself. Furthermore, voice signatures need to be updated each time a new SSV model replaces an old one in a system, as the voice signatures might not match anymore. This means that the voice signatures have to be recalculated so they can be compared to the voice signatures coming from the new model. Compared to this, reconstructed speech does not have to be resynthesized from the converted speech again when there is an SSV model update, making SSR more flexible than SSV.

Cai et al. [7] proposed a unique VC method which is capable of inverting its own synthesized mel-spectrograms back into the source speech mel-spectrogram. The limiting factor of this approach is that it is only capable of recovering source speech from its own output. It is incapable of reconstructing source speech from converted speech coming from different VC methods.

VoxTracer [8] is a component placed after a VC method in order to introduce extra source speaker information into converted speech. While VoxTracer relies on injecting speaker identity into VC output for reconstruction, later studies [2-4] show that source speaker identity can still be extracted from unaltered converted speech. Nonetheless, the authors propose an approach to source speech reconstruction. However, their SSR approach relies on the source speaker identity being introduced into the voice-converted utterance.

4. PROPOSED APPROACH

We propose an approach which only utilizes the converted utterance and a trained SSV model to reconstruct the original speech. The proposed approach is shown in Fig. 2.

The core idea of the proposed approach is that the content of the source speech is completely preserved in the converted utterance. The source speaker style is introduced by a voice signature extracted by an SSV as seen in the figure. The feasibility of this approach is entirely dependent on the SSV system extracting voice signatures which correctly represent the source speaker.

Applicability. This approach is applicable to any VC method, just like VoxTracer is applicable to any VC method – it is model agnostic. It is always possible to train an SSV model to extract identities from converted samples if the model is open-source. The main benefit of this approach is that further research to make SSV more robust to unseen VC models will improve the robustness of this approach by default. Furthermore, the rest of the network is unaffected by encountering unseen VC models. Compression is also not an issue, as shown by Deng et al. [2].

Fig. 2: Proposed approach to source speech reconstruction for any particular VC method. The source speaker identity is extracted using an SSV module in the form of an embedding. The performance of the SSV can be enhanced using target speaker to filter out the style introduced into the converted sample as proposed by Deng et al. [2]. The content is extracted from the converted speech itself. Essentially, the reconstruction is done by performing another voice conversion back into the style of the source speaker.

Component choice. For the SSV, we propose training a CA-MHFA [9] with 64 heads using a WavLM Large [10] extractor on AAM [11] loss with a margin of 0.2 and scale of 32. CA-MHFA’s performance has not been studied for the SSV task and could provide further contribution to my research. WavLM is a standard extractor for pooling methods. AAM is a standard loss function employed in SSV. For SSR, we could employ the FreeVC model architecture. The dataset used for training SSV is the one provided in the SLT SST Challenge [4]. For SSR, a parallel dataset containing source speech is to be constructed to complement the SLT SSTC dataset in order to train the SSR synthesizer. The synthesizer itself is to be trained using a reconstruction loss, mirroring the training scheme of VC methods. The training scheme itself is that of a voice conversion method with a pre-trained speaker encoder. The synthesizer must learn to introduce the style of the source speaker from pre-trained embeddings in order to match the source speech.

Evaluation. To measure source speaker similarity in reconstructed speech, EER will be measured on scores extracted by an automatic speaker verification system (TitaNet [12]). Word Error Rate (WER) will be measured to ensure the content of the original speech is preserved. The measurement will be done using a speech recognition system (Whisper [13]).

6. CONCLUSION

We summarize the current state of source speaker tracing – a task for identifying source speakers of a synthesized utterance. We discuss the advantages and disadvantages of different approaches. Finally, we propose a general, model-agnostic approach to source speech reconstruction, which we are currently developing. This approach could provide a more flexible result compared to voice signatures extracted by source speaker verification whilst maintaining the generalizability to be employed against the majority of VC methods.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Although SST can be beneficial in exposing the identities of bad actors, it can also be used maliciously to de-anonymize the voice-converted speech of a victim. Imagine a scenario where a victim unintentionally uses a voice conversion method for anonymization. Note that voice conversion methods are meant to spoof, not anonymize. An adversary may use a source speaker identification method to expose the identity of the victim in order to harm them (doxxing).

Preventing the exploitation of SST tools by attackers is not the goal of this paper. However, the authors acknowledge the need for further research in this area. For now, caution is encouraged; anonymization tools should be utilized by the users to mitigate such attacks.

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